

DETERMINATION OF OPTIMAL SUBSIDIES FOR BALANCING LOCAL SUPPLY/DEMAND OF BIOMASS PRODUCTS WITHIN A REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIC PLAN

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ABSTRACT: Under the assumption that energy crop farmers believe the price in the previous period will prevail in the current period as well, adjusting their cultivation species accordingly, the biomass market may exhibit instability. In the present work, optimal subsidy I_{opt} is determined for balancing local supply/demand of biomass products for avoiding such instability while ensuring adequacy of biomass inventory for feeding continuously a biomass processing unit. The I_{opt} model is implemented for parameter values referring to Greek biomass-to-energy market, which appears to be a developing sector although the economy (as a whole) is in recession during the last two years. It is also shown that optimization of the subsidy required to balance local supply/demand of biomass products depends on capacity optimization of the biomass processing plant under consideration, within a strategic plan for regional development that should put emphasis on (i) the improvement of the rural roads network to minimize transportation costs and (ii) the diffusion of information about conditions recommended for biomass storing in open air to avoid enzymatic hydrolysis which deteriorates the quality of raw material and decreases the efficiency of the processing unit.

Keywords: biomass, demand, economical aspects, energy, strategy, supply.

1 INTRODUCTORY ANALYSIS

Biomass demand for downstream products may exceed the supply corresponding to market equilibrium as expected before harvesting (e.g., to obtain an energy crop). In such a case (i.e., when the supply actually harvested falls short of the intended supply), the market period supply (MPS) function, or the corresponding curve in the familiar Quantity Q – Price P diagram, shifts to a below equilibrium (denoted by Q_0 for price P_0) output of Q_1 , generating an above equilibrium price of P_1 . Thinking that this price is going to remain in the next agricultural period, farmers plan an above equilibrium output of Q_2 , which, in its turn, assuming their intentions are exactly realized, generates a below equilibrium price of P_2 , and so on. The repeated cycles corresponding to successive agricultural periods, may lead either to convergence towards an equilibrium or to divergence contributing to market instability, as shown in Fig. 1, according to the ‘Cobweb’ model, also known as ‘Cobweb Theorem’ in Economics [1-4].

The present work deals with the application of this model or theorem to energy crops within an agricultural local economy, common in several regions of the Mediterranean Countries. It is proved that by granting an optimal subsidy I_{opt} , we can avoid market instability, expected to occur when the elasticity of demand is lower than the elasticity of supply. The same method can be used to accelerate convergence (or ‘self-damping’) towards equilibrium in order to minimize the duration that the biomass-to-energy market in disequilibrium; in this case, the rate of approaching equilibrium is estimated as a function of the supply and demand parameters.

2 METHODOLOGY

The optimal value I_{opt} is determined as a function of (a) the fraction K of the conventional energy saving denoted by F (in monetary units, for the first year of the normal operation of the biomass-to-energy installation) to

Figure 1: Application of a Cobweb model to energy crop leading to (top) divergence, i.e., market instability, since the elasticity of demand is lower than the elasticity of supply and (bottom) convergence, i.e., market stability, since the elasticity of demand is higher than the elasticity of supply.

be deducted annually by the State from its welfare budget; (b) the annual increase g of F , giving rise to an arithmetic series with a ratio gF ; (c) the capital S to be invested; (d) the time horizon t of the investment, in years; (e) the rate of interest i (for estimating money equivalence over time) and the rate of return r on the best alternative investment (called the 'second best' in comparison with the first best for the State, which is the subsidized project), both annually expressed.

Referring all gains U_i at the end of a t years period, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= KF(1+i)^{t-1} \\ U_2 &= KF(1+i)^{t-2}(1+g) \\ U_3 &= KF(1+i)^{t-3}(1+2g) \\ &\dots\dots\dots \\ U_t &= \underline{KF(1+i)^{t-1}[1+(t-1)g]} \end{aligned}$$

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^t U_i = KF(1+i)^{t-1} \times \left[1 + \frac{1+g}{1+i} + \frac{1+2g}{(1+i)^2} + \dots + \frac{1+(t-1)g}{(1+i)^{t-1}} \right] \quad (1)$$

By setting $1/(1+i) = x$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} U &= KFx^{1-t} [1 + (1+g)x + (1+2g)x^2 + \dots + (1+(t-1)g)x^{t-1}] \\ U &= KFx^{1-t} [(1+x+x^2+\dots+x^{t-1}) + gxT] \\ U &= KFx^{1-t} \left[\frac{x^{t-1}x-1}{x-1} + gxT \right] \end{aligned}$$

where

$$T = 1 + 2x + 3x^2 + \dots + (t-1)x^{t-2} \quad (2)$$

For the calculation of T , which is an arithmetic-geometric series, we work as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} xT &= x + 2x^2 + 3x^3 + \dots + (t-1)x^{t-1} \\ (1-x)T &= [1+x+x^2+\dots+x^{t-2}] - (t-1)x^{t-1} \end{aligned}$$

The expression within the brackets is a geometric series, the sum of which is given by $(x^{t-2}x - a)/(x-1)$, where $a = 1$ and $x = 1/(1+i)$, i.e., the first term and the constant multiplier (or ratio), respectively. Thus, the last equation is rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} (1-x)T &= \frac{x^{t-1}-1}{x-1} - (t-1)x^{t-1} \\ \text{or} \\ T &= \frac{1-x^{t-1}}{(x-1)^2} + \frac{(t-1)x^{t-1}}{x-1} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

By inserting this expression in equation (1), we obtain:

$$U = KFx^{1-t} \left[\frac{x^t-1}{x-1} + gx \left(\frac{1-x^{t-1}}{(x-1)^2} + \frac{(t-1)x^{t-1}}{x-1} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where F is the first year energy cost saving and t the time periods (actually dimensionless) taken into account. On the other hand, we can estimate the opportunity cost as the potential loss Y that is the value of the alternatives or other opportunities which have to be foregone in order to subsidize an energy saving investment of initial capital S , with an amount of money $I \times S$. If r is the return on the best alternative investment for the subsidized fraction $I.S$, then Y , expressed at the end of a t years period (or t dimensionless periods, in general), is given by the following relation:

$$Y = IS(1+r)^t \quad (5)$$

Obviously, the optimal value of I is obtained for $U = Y$, so neither the State nor the investor make a surplus profit causing a corresponding loss to the other part (condition of equilibrium [5]). From the equations (4) and (5), we obtain

$$U = Y$$

or

$$KFx^{1-t} \left[\frac{x^t-1}{x-1} + gx \left(\frac{1-x^{t-1}}{(x-1)^2} + \frac{(t-1)x^{t-1}}{x-1} \right) \right] = I_{opt}S(1+r)^t \quad (6)$$

$$I_{opt} = \frac{K \cdot F \cdot x^{1-t} \left[\frac{x^t-1}{x-1} + gx \left(\frac{1-x^{t-1}}{(x-1)^2} + \frac{(t-1)x^{t-1}}{x-1} \right) \right]}{S(1+r)^t} \quad (7)$$

This is a normative model (coming from the corresponding positive relations, through the equilibrium condition $U = Y$, which introduces specific policy making), determining I_{opt} under a new discipline of conventional energy cost increase over time [6]. In case that biomass market instability prevails, of the kind described in Introductory Analysis and illustrated in the top diagram of Fig. 1, then, by increasing external support through subsidy, two paths exist in order to stabilize the market: (i) solely increase of biomass demand elasticity when the subsidy granted for setting up the biomass processing unit contributes to increased scale economies, and (ii) combination of this increase with decrease of biomass supply elasticity; the latter can be achieved by subsidizing the improvement of the rural roads transportation network towards the biomass processing unit. Each path passes through a critical point, where neither divergence nor convergence occurs, as shown in Fig. 2. The determination of the minimum subsidy required to reach this critical point is of significant importance for biomass policymaking: if subsidy to the processing unit is not adequate for such an achievement, then subsidizing directly infrastructure development dedicated to biomass production/transportation oriented investment should be considered.

Evidently, subsidies taking into account contracts between farmers, who supply energy crops, and industry, that is the demand-side player (acting also as a supplier to the final customers of the biomass-to-energy markets) tend to damp the cobweb cycle and generally to stabilize the market by following a regional development strategic plan, which the subsidy is part of.

Figure 2: Application of a Cobweb model to energy crop leading to continuous cycle of constant magnitude oscillations by (top) increasing solely biomass demand elasticity and (bottom) decreasing supply elasticity when subsidy granted to the biomass processing unit is not enough to avoid market instability due to divergence, as shown in the top diagram of Fig. 1.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

An implementation of I_{opt} determination is subsequently presented for parameter values referring to Greek biomass-to-energy market ($F/S=0.11-0.14$, $K=0.12$, $r=0.045$, $g=0.65$, $t=25$, $i=0.015$), which appears to be a developing sector although the economy (as a whole) is in recession during the last two years. The results are shown graphically in Figs 3 and 4, under the form of sensitivity analysis diagrams, where all parameters, except the one examined each time, take their central values as quoted above.

The zone in gray is due to the interval number F/S used for taking into account uncertainty. Since interval bounds of numerical results may be overestimated, especially when the number of intermediate arithmetic calculations carried out to reach the final result is big, we use algorithms to prevent the growth of interval width, as shown in [7].

It is worthwhile noting that in most cases $I_{opt} < 0.40$, which is the upper limit for usual subsidization in Greece, while it can be higher when the investment is incorporated within a regional development strategic plan.

Figure 3: Monoparametric sensitivity analysis indicating the dependence of optimal subsidy I_{opt} on r , g , t , i , for range values representative of the Greek biomass-to-energy potential market.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

The capital S required for the investment is a function of the biomass processing capacity C of the industrial plant under consideration. The optimal value C_{opt} can be determined as an equilibrium point in the trade off between expenditures E_1 for biomass transportation and E_2 for biomass processing. The first variable, E_1 , is an increasing function of C with an increasing rate (i.e., $dE_1/dC > 0$ and $d^2E_1/dC^2 > 0$), since higher C -values require transportation from longer

Figure 4: First and second order sensitivity analysis (top and bottom diagram, respectively) of optimal subsidy I_{opt} in the region $P_0 \pm 0.25P_0$, where P_0 is the mean value of parameter P (i.e., r , g , t , i); on the horizontal axis, the dimensionless values $p = P/P_0$ are quoted.

distance in order to form the biomass inventory that is necessary for continuous fuel production; moreover, the expenditure for biomass collection is proportional to the area, which is covered by either cultivated energy plants or lignocellulosic residues, and this area is a parabolic function of distance from the processing industrial unit, implying non-linear dependence of E_1 on C . On the other hand, the second variable, E_2 , is a decreasing function of C with an increasing algebraic or decreasing absolute rate (i.e., $dE_2/dC < 0$ and $d^2E_2/dC^2 > 0$ or $d|dE_2/dC|/dC < 0$) because of the validity of the exponential function giving the intensity of scale economies, which are more expressed in the region of low C -values, as shown in the next paragraph. The C_{opt} -value is determined at $E_{min} = (E_1 + E_2)_{min}$ or $d(E_1 + E_2)/dC = 0$ or $ME_1 = ME_2$, where $ME_1 = dE_1/dC$ and $ME_2 = |dE_2/dC|$ are the marginal values of E_1 and E_2 , respectively. In case of significant oil price increase, implying respective increase of transportation cost, the E_1 -curve moves upwards becoming steeper at the same time, because increase is expected to be more expressed in the region of high C -values corresponding to longer distance from the biomass processing unit; since this industrial unit is located at the most accessible point, the transportation effort per distance unit increases implying higher fuel consumption in countries like Greece where the quality of rural roads network worsens significantly when we go away from urban areas. As a result, C_{opt} is shifting to C'_{opt} , where $C'_{opt} < C_{opt}$, as shown in Fig. 5a. On the contrary, if this network is expected to be improved in the near future by a corresponding provision within regional development strategic plan, the E_1 -curve will eventually move downwards becoming more flat at the same time, because of the transportation cost decrease, which is most likely to exhibit larger differences in the region of high C -values for the reason quoted above; as a result C_{opt} is shifting to C''_{opt} , where

Figure 5: Dependence of biomass transportation expenditure E_1 on shifting of optimal biomass processing capacity C_{opt} in case of (a) significant oil price increase and (b) rural roads network improvement within a regional development strategic plan.

$C''_{opt} > C_{opt}$, as shown in Fig. 5b.

It is worthwhile noting that the scale economies (mentioned above to justify the features of the E_2 -curve) in the biomass processing unit depend heavily on the kind of final output of the processing plant. Using the classical expression (8) to estimate the scale economies index b , according to numerical data (suitable only for a rough approximation) provided in technical literature [8], we obtain the following values for a biomass-based industrial plant producing energy

$$(S/S_0) = (C/C_0)^b \Rightarrow \ln(S/S_0) = b \ln(C/C_0) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Electrical (P), } b = \frac{\ln(50/4)}{\ln(25/2)} = 1$$

$$\text{Thermal (H), } b = \frac{\ln(10/1.5)}{\ln(22/1.5)} = 0.71$$

$$\text{Combined (CHP), } b = \frac{\ln(25/5)}{\ln(8.289/1.050)} = 0.78$$

which means that a biomass-based industrial plant exhibits maximum scale economies when performing within a thermal process. It is worthwhile noting that, in the case of CHP, the total power has been estimated by using the equivalence 1 MW=3.413 million Btu/h.

We can obtain a more reliable/exact approximation of b by referring to the specific technology used to electricity production, according to numerical data found in [9] as follows:

I. Steam Rankine cycle,

$$b = \frac{\ln(82.35/35.10)}{\ln(50/10)} = 0.53$$

II. Biomass gasifier under atmospheric pressure,

$$b = \frac{\ln(77.28/25.77)}{\ln(60/10)} = 0.61$$

III. Biomass gasifier with filter hot gas cleanup,

$$b = \frac{\ln(85.50/54.00)}{\ln(60/30)} = 0.66$$

which means that a biomass-based industrial plant exhibits maximum scale economies when using a Steam Rankine cycle; the corresponding scale economies index/factor $b=0.53$ is considerably lower than the value $b=0.85$ reported for processes involving the handling of solids [10, 11], moderately lower than the mean value $b=0.70$ found to be approximately valid for a big number of chemical processing units [12-14], and slightly lower than the values suggested in the initial articles by Williams and Chilton [15, 16]. In case that more than two points are available, we can apply common unweighted and weighted least squares regression for the linear model without and with constant term, to obtain b -estimates according to (9) and (11), respectively (derived from the normal equations valid for the corresponding one- and-two parameter models (8) and (10)).

$$b = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \ln(C_i/C_0) \ln(S_i/S_0)}{\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [\ln(C_i/C_0)]^2} \quad (9)$$

$$S = S_0 (C/C_0)^b \Rightarrow \ln S = \ln S_0 + b \ln(C/C_0) \quad (10)$$

$$b = \frac{1}{D} \left| \begin{array}{cc} n & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (\ln S_i) \\ \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [\ln(C_i/C_0)] & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [\ln(C_i/C_0) \ln S_i] \end{array} \right| \quad (11)$$

$$D = \left| \begin{array}{cc} n & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (\ln C_i/C_0) \\ \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [\ln(C_i/C_0)] & \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} [\ln(C_i/C_0)]^2 \end{array} \right|$$

Finally, we can obtain a better approximation of the b -value by non-linear regression of the original model (8) by applying the 'relative least squares' method in order to put emphasis on the low-capacity region and avoid statistical errors caused by linearization, since in the latter case fitting refers to logarithms of the variables and not to the variables themselves; in such a case, the b -value is estimated by solving numerically (e.g., applying bisection or Newton method) the following equation, which is derived from the corresponding system of normal equations, where only one of them is non-linear:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (C_i/C_0)^b / S_i \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (C_i/C_0)^{2b} \ln(C_i/C_0) / S_i^2 - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (C_i/C_0)^{2b} / S_i^2 \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (C_i/C_0)^b \ln(C_i/C_0) / S_i = 0$$

In conclusion, optimization of the subsidy required to balance local supply/demand of biomass products depends on capacity optimization of the biomass processing plant under consideration (producing either energy/fuels or new materials within a framework of Industrial Ecology [17-26], within a strategic plan for regional development that should put emphasis on (i) the improvement of the rural roads network to minimize transportation costs and (ii) the diffusion of information about conditions recommended for biomass storing in open air to avoid enzymatic hydrolysis which deteriorates the quality of raw material and decreases the efficiency of the processing unit.

It is also proved that subsidies taking into account contracts between farmers, who supply energy crops, and industry, that is the demand-side player (acting also as a supplier to the final customers of the biomass-to-energy markets) tend to damp the cobweb cycle and generally to stabilize the market by following the regional development strategic plan, which the subsidy is part of.

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